

Refactorings not investigated by the final set of Papers

Fowler Refactoring	LI	AI	Fowler Refactoring	LI	AI
Change Value to Reference	✓		Collapse Hierarchy	✓	
Combine Functions into Class	✓	✓	Combine Functions into Transform	✓	
Consolidate Conditional Expression	✓		Decompose Conditional	✓	
Encapsulate Collection	✓		Encapsulate Record	✓	
Extract Variable	✓		Hide Delegate	✓	✓
Inline Class	✓		Inline Variable	✓	
Introduce Assertion	✓		Introduce Special Case	✓	
Move Statements into Function	✓		Move Statements to Callers	✓	
Parameterize Function	✓	✓	Pull Up Constructor Body	✓	
Remove Dead Code	✓		Remove Flag Argument	✓	
Remove Middle Man	✓	✓	Remove Setting Method	✓	
Remove Subclass	✓	✓	Rename Variable	✓	
Replace Command with Function	✓	✓	Replace Conditional with Polymorphism	✓	
Replace Constructor with Factory Function	✓	✓	Replace Control Flag with Break	✓	
Replace Derived Variable with Query	✓		Replace Error Code with Exception	✓	
Replace Exception with Precheck	✓		Replace Inline Code with Function Call	✓	
Replace Loop with Pipeline	✓		Replace Magic Literal	✓	
Replace Nested Conditional with Guard Clauses	✓		Replace Parameter with Query	✓	✓
Replace Primitive with Object	✓		Replace Query with Parameter	✓	✓
Replace Subclass with Delegate	✓	✓	Replace Superclass with Delegate	✓	✓
Replace Inheritance with Delegation	✓		Return Modified Value	✓	
Separate Query from Modifier	✓		Slide Statements	✓	
Split Loop	✓		Split Phase	✓	
Split Variable	✓	✓			